

On Compounding, Zone refining, and Crystal growing of Indium Antimonide

R. KRISHNASWAMY

Technical Physics Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre Trombay, Bombay 400085

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The intermetallic compound Indium Antimonide belonging to gr.III-gr.V of the periodic table has been studied. The compounding techniques, methods used to overcome crucible cracking, Zone refining operations and their effect on physical parameters like resistivity, and Bridgman method of crystal growing are described.

THE compound semiconductor indium antimonide is one of the III-V compounds, studied because of its low melting point, (523°) relative ease of preparation of the compound compared to other compounds, small energy gap (0.17 ev) high electron mobility (65000 cm/v-sec) and consequently high Hall efficiency (about 300 times that of germanium). Indium antimonide finds applications in Hall effect flux meter for magnetic measurement, photoconductor, infrared detector, measurements of small currents, and in magnetoresistor mainly because of the above properties. The energy gap being small, InSb devices suffer much from temperature variation in Hall output (2% for InSb compared to 0.1% for InAs) Consequently InSb devices are used at constant temperature atmosphere.

The physical parameters are shown in Table 1. This paper deals with the compounding techniques used, and methods developed to avoid crucible cracking subsequent on cooling, zone refining operations, resistivity determinations, Hall coefficient measurements and crystal growing by Bridgman method.

Compound Formation

The metal indium and antimony belong to group III and V of the periodic table. They form a compound covalently bonded at 523° and in a stoichiometric ratio (50 : 50 atomic percentage). The compound itself is prepared from very high purity indium and antimony (total metallic impurities 10 ppm in each) in stoichiometric ratio.^{2,6} The materials were preferably etched and dried using high purity (electronic grade) hydrochloric acid and all the operations were done in dust proof chamber to prevent contamination. It is sealed in vacuum at a pressure of 10^{-5} mm. of Hg. in a quartz crucible using a rotary pump and a diffusion pump with liquid air trap. A standard type of pot furnace using nichrome heaters was used to provide a constant temperature of 600° over the whole length (10") of crucible. A shaking mechanism using a spring loaded disc attached to a slow speed motor was used to provide vertical agitation for better mixing, and to expel trapped gases if any. The melting is done in a vertical position for about four hours and

the melt was cooled. It was found by observation, that invariably the quartz container cracks, independent of the rate of cooling and cannot be avoided as the InSb expands on cooling.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS

Material	Energy gap ev.	Mobility μ cm ² /volt/sec.	m.p.°C
InSb	0.17	65,000	523
InAs	0.33	23,000	936
Ge	0.66	3,600	958

Fig. 1 Pyrolytic Decomposition of Carbon

This problem was solved by adopting two methods. As soon as the melting was complete the crucible was kept in a horizontal position in the furnace itself and allowed to cool. As there was sufficient space above the melt to expand, there was no cracking of the crucible for repeated trials. The second method tried successfully was the deposition of pyrolytically decomposed carbon on the inner walls of the crucible before loading. (Fig. 1). The crucible was kept in a pot furnace at about 800° in a continuous vacuum of 10^{-3} mm. of mercury (With a liquid air trap). Toluene was allowed to evaporate into the crucible for a short time (5 sec.) and then disconnected by the 3 way stop cock mechanism. When toluene-crucible system is open the crucible vacuum system is closed simultaneously by

arranging the stop cock connections. As soon as the operation is over, the crucible is returned to the vacuum system, simultaneously closing the toluene-crucible system. In no case toluene vessel is directly connected to the vacuum system. A smooth fine translucent coating of carbon was obtained. For a fairly translucent coating the operation has to be repeated 8 to 10 times. At lower temperatures the coating was not good. Temperatures beyond 800° were not tried. On a number of trials, the crucible did not crack on cooling, the compound did not stick to glass, which it otherwise used to and it was easily removed by gentle tapping ensuring every time an unbroken ingot with a smooth surface.

The mechanism is, the smooth and even surface of the coating which the glass does not possess otherwise, allows the melt to expand along its sides towards the top as the solidification is only continuous and not instantaneous. The cooling rate of about 2V/10 min (10°C/10 min was found to be suitable).

Zone Refining : Random resistivity studies showed the necessity of further purification by zone refining to decrease the concentration of the carriers. Impurities tend to segregate in the liquid phase in the melt making the solid phase purer.

$$K_{\text{eff}} = \frac{\text{(Conc. of impurities in the solid)}}{\text{(Conc. of impurities in the liquid)}}$$

Segregation coefficients for some common impurities have been reported to be approximately 0.6 and above¹. Consequently, very large numbers of passes become necessary to remove slightly segregated impurities. Three identical resistance heaters with a zone length of 2.25 cms. and interzonal distance of 11.25 cms. were used. Zone lengths equal to the diameter of the tube was found to be difficult because for thinner heaters the zone was diffused (not sharp) and heater design with adequate insulation poses a problem. All the heaters were mounted on a Syndanyo platform coupled to two motors by leadscrew and spurgears. A forward linear speed

Fig. 2 Resistivity Measurements Variation with Temp. Zone Refined Sample 30 Passes

Fig. 3 Variation of Resistivity with No. of Zone Passes- Samples Refined in Vacuum T= 292°K

FIG 5 ZONE MELTING

of 10 cms., 7½ cms., 5 cms. per hour and a constant backward speed of 10 cms. per minute were provided by the refiner. A tilt⁴ of 5° was given at the starting end to avoid matter transport. Faster speeds were used in the initial stages (Upto 15 passes) and slower speeds were used in the last stages. All the samples were refined in the horizontal position, in a long, pointed edged (30°) quartz crucible (length 10", dia. 15 m/m), sealed in a vacuum of 10⁻⁵ cm. of Hg. Two separate samples one for resistivity variation with temperature and other with number of zone passes were studied. Resistivities were measured with a 4 probe resistivity meter. The results and set up are shown in Figures 2, 3, 4, and 5.

Hall Effect Studies

Hall effect studies were done to determine the carrier concentration. Several Hall probes were made from zone refined bars. The bars were wax mounted and first cut to 1 mm×6 mm×2mm (thickness, length and breadth respectively) using a thin (0.007") diamond wheel cutter, with lubricant. Further reduced to 0.35 mm by emery polishing (600 number) in a glove box. Specimens were washed repeatedly in deionised water and finally rinsed in high purity acetone. Mounted on a Hall probe printed circuit and the 4 connections

were soldered with indium solder. Experimental values for two samples are given in Table 2. The Hall voltage increases with decreasing thickness. The effect is shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6 Magnetic Field vs Hall Output (Effect of Thickness)

well insulated furnaces, separated by a syndanyo baffle. The top furnace was used for melting the sample and kept sufficiently above the melting point of InSb (600° for a length of 10"). The bottom furnace was used for providing slow cooling, and was wound closely at the top and sparsely at the bottom. The rate of temperature fall was adjusted by baffles, as well as by adjusting the power (from constant voltage source) to the top and bottom furnaces (The furnace assembly and the temperature profile is shown in Figs. 7 and 8). Initially a sudden temperature fall of 100°/inch at the baffle and gradual cooling afterwards was tried without success. A rate of fall of 60-70°/inch at the baffle was found to be satisfactory. The expansion of InSb on cooling was

Fig. 7 Bridgman Furnace Details

Fig. 8 Temp Profile-Bridgman Furnace

Crystal Growing

Indium antimonide can be crystal grown by the method of Czochralski crystal pulling⁵. The evaporation of antimony is about 0.1% but as the solubility of excess constituent in the compound is negligible, stoichiometry is not altered. Crystal pulling of InSb was tried without much success, because of antimony evaporation and poor visibility. An alternate method of crystal growing by Bridgman method was tried with good results. The furnace assembly consisted of two

avoided by pyrolytically coating carbon on the walls of the crucible (ref: compound formation). There was absolutely no cracking of the crucible for all the trials. A pointed shaped bottom (30°) was used to provide seeding. The samples were etched with nitric acid and hydrofluoric⁷ acid mixture (5 HF : 5HNO₃ : 2H₂O) for 10 secs and studied under the microscope for etch patterns. It showed uniform grain structure without grain boundaries. Some samples were tested for X-ray patterns and found to be single crystals.

TABLE 2—HALL VOLTAGES, HALL COEFFICIENTS, AND VARIATION WITH MAGNETIC FIELD.

Sample I Thickness 0.22 MM, Resistive voltage-14 mV, Control current-100 mA, Resistivity-19.5 m. ohms (295°K)

No.	Magnetic field of electromagnet in Gauss.	Out put voltage m.V.	Hall Voltage. mV.	Hall coefficient $\times 10^2$ (cm ² /coulomb)
1.	5000	145	131	5.764
2.	7500	195	181	4.840
3.	9500	220	206	4.770
4.	10500	230	216	4.520
5.	11500	240	226	4.410

Number of carriers $1.342 \times 10^{18}/\text{ml.}$
 Hall Mobility $2.388 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^2/\text{volt second}$
 Material is not doped. Temperature 300°K.

Sample II Thickness 0.33 mm, Resistive voltage-5 mV, Control current-100 mA, Resistivity-12.5 m. ohms. (295°K)

1.	4000	47.5	42.5	3.57
2.	6500	80.0	75.0	4.06
3.	8575	95.0	90.0	3.57
4.	10000	110.0	105	3.63
5.	11000	122	117	3.66
6.	12000	130	125	3.58
7.	12500	140	135	3.60

Number of carriers $1.72 \times 10^{18}/\text{ml.}$
 Hall mobility $3.75 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^2/\text{volt second}$
 Material is not doped. Temperature 300°K.
 Hall coefficient values are lower for sample II as it is less pure than I.

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